

Exploring Gender Differences in Buying Intention Towards Organic Food: An Application of the Theory of Planned Behavior

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Abstract This research delves into how gender shapes buying intentions toward organic food, using the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as a guiding framework. By analyzing gender as a moderating factor, the study explores its influence on key TPB components: attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. The results indicate that gender plays a crucial role in strengthening the link between attitudes towards organic food and purchase intentions, although it doesn't significantly affect the other factors. These findings offer valuable insights for marketers and policymakers aiming to tailor organic food campaigns to gender-specific preferences.

Keywords Organic Food, Buying Intention, Gender Differences, Theory of Planned Behavior, Moderating Variable, Regression Analysis.

Introduction

Research Background

Over the past decade, the global organic food market has seen remarkable growth, fueled by a rising awareness among consumers about the importance of health, environmental sustainability, and food safety. Organic food consumption is often linked to a variety of positive outcomes, including reduced exposure to pesticides, better nutrition, and support for sustainable agricultural practices. Despite these benefits, the buying intentions towards organic food vary significantly among different consumer segments. Understanding the factors influencing these intentions is crucial for marketers and policymakers aiming to promote organic food products effectively.

Statement of the Problem

While many studies have used the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) to explore consumer intentions in various settings, there's still a lack of research focusing on how gender influences these intentions, especially in the organic food sector. Since men and women may perceive the benefits of organic food differently, it's important to investigate how gender shapes key TPB factors—attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control—in the context of organic food choices.

Objective of study

This study aims to accomplish the following objectives:

1. To assess whether gender moderates the relationship between attitude towards organic food and buying intentions.
2. To determine if gender moderates the influence of subjective norm on buying intentions towards organic food.
3. To evaluate whether gender moderates the effect of perceived behavioral control on buying intentions towards organic food.

Significance of the Study

This research adds to our understanding of consumer behavior by exploring how gender influences the decision to purchase organic food. By focusing on the differences between men and women, the study offers practical insights for marketers and policymakers to create more effective and targeted strategies. These insights can help in crafting marketing campaigns that resonate with the unique preferences and motivations of both male and female consumers, ultimately supporting the growth of the organic food market.

Review of Literature

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and Consumer Behavior

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), introduced by Ajzen (1991), is a comprehensive framework for understanding and predicting human behavior. According to TPB, behavior is influenced by behavioral intentions, which are shaped by three main constructs: attitude towards the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. The versatility of TPB has been demonstrated across various domains, including health behaviors, environmental actions, and consumer purchasing decisions (Armitage & Conner, 2001). Recent research has extended TPB by incorporating factors such as environmental concerns, food safety, and exploratory buying traits, thereby enhancing its applicability in predicting organic food purchase intentions (Ahmed et al., 2021; Samala, 2021; Sadiq et al., 2021).

Attitude Towards Organic Food

Attitude towards a behavior reflects an individual's positive or negative evaluation of that behavior (Ajzen, 1991). In the realm of organic food, attitudes are commonly influenced by perceptions related to health benefits, environmental sustainability, and food safety (Hughner et al., 2007). A positive attitude towards organic food is a strong predictor of purchase intention (Aertsens et al., 2009; Padel & Foster, 2005). Research in India by Singh and Verma (2017) identified health and safety concerns as key factors driving consumers' organic food choices. Building on this, Matharu et al. (2021) highlighted that attitudes significantly affect organic food purchase intentions and behavior among young Indian consumers. Additionally, Sadiq et al. (2021) found that utilitarian values, which shape attitudes, exert a greater influence on organic food consumption intentions than hedonic values.

Subjective Norms

Subjective norms refer to the social pressure individuals perceive to either engage in or refrain from a particular behavior (Ajzen, 1991). In the context of organic food purchases, subjective norms encompass the influence of family, friends, and societal expectations. In collectivist cultures, where social influence is prominent, subjective norms significantly affect organic food purchasing decisions (Dean et al., 2008; Tarkiainen & Sundqvist, 2005). In India, Khare (2015) found that social factors play a crucial role in shaping consumers' choices to buy organic products. Matharu et al. (2021) also emphasized the significant impact of subjective norms on organic food purchase intentions, with Ahmed et al. (2021) noting that environmental awareness moderates this influence among young consumers.

Perceived Behavioral Control

Perceived behavioral control pertains to an individual's perception of the ease or difficulty of performing a behavior, which influences both their intentions and actual actions. If consumers perceive organic food purchasing as easy and affordable, they are more likely to intend to buy and follow through with the purchase (Ajzen, 1991). Studies have shown a positive link between higher perceived control and stronger intentions to purchase organic food (Arvola et al., 2008; Vermeir & Verbeke, 2008). In India, Paul, Modi, and Patel (2016) highlighted that perceived behavioral control is a critical predictor of green product consumption, emphasizing the importance of accessibility to organic products. Furthermore, Sadiq et al. (2021) found that exploratory information-seeking traits enhance the relationship between perceived behavioral control and purchase intentions. Ahmed et al. (2021) also confirmed that perceived behavioral control positively influences purchase intention, with environmental awareness boosting this effect.

Gender Differences in Consumer Behavior

Research has consistently shown that men and women often have differing motivations and behaviors when it comes to purchasing (Meyers-Levy & Loken, 2015). In the context of organic food, women are generally more focused on health and environmental aspects, leading to more positive attitudes towards organic products compared to men (Lockie et

al., 2004; Bravo et al., 2013). Similarly Gundala et al (2022) found that males and females differ in purchasing intention toward organic food.

Role of Gender in TPB Constructs

The moderating role of gender in TPB constructs has been explored in various studies, indicating that gender can affect the strength and direction of relationships between attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (Venkatesh & Morris, 2000). For instance, gender differences in attitudes towards organic food can significantly impact buying intentions, with women generally exhibiting more positive attitudes and higher purchase intentions (Lockie et al., 2004; Bravo et al., 2013). Research in India by Khare (2015) and Paul et al. (2016) has demonstrated that gender moderates the relationship between TPB constructs and consumer behavior, with women showing stronger links between attitudes and purchase intentions. Kaur et al. (2022) further emphasized that demographic variables play a significant role in influencing green buying intentions, underscoring the importance of demographic factors in shaping consumer behavior.

Methodology

Research Design

This study takes an exploratory approach to look at how gender affects people's intentions to buy organic food, using the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as a framework. The goal is to uncover and understand how attitudes, social influences, and perceptions of control differ between men and women, and how these differences shape their willingness to purchase organic food.

Sample Design

The study was conducted with a final sample size of 150 respondents, consisting of an equal number of male and female participants (75 males and 75 females). A purposive sampling technique was employed to ensure that the sample included individuals who have an awareness of organic food and are potential buyers. This approach allowed for the selection of respondents who could provide relevant insights into the research questions.

Data Collection

Data was collected using a detailed questionnaire based on key ideas from the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB): attitudes, social influences, and perceived control, along with buying intentions. The questionnaire also included questions about basic details like gender. To ensure the measures were reliable and accurate, the researchers used questions from established sources.

The questionnaire was distributed both online and in-person to reach a broad and varied group of people. Respondents were informed about the study's purpose and were assured that their answers would be kept confidential.

Analysis

Data Analysis

The data analysis was done using SPSS software. First, the researchers used descriptive statistics to summarize the respondents' demographic details. They then used regression analysis to test their hypotheses, focusing on how gender affects the results.

To see if gender played a role, the researchers looked at how gender interacted with each TPB factor. They checked whether these interactions were significant to understand if gender influenced the relationship between these factors and buying intentions.

Validity and Reliability

To ensure the questionnaire was reliable, questions were based on scales that had been tested before in TPB studies. A pilot study with 30 people was conducted to check if the questions were clear and relevant, and adjustments were made based on the feedback received.

Reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha to check if the questions within each TPB factor were consistent. A standard of 0.70 was used to confirm that each factor was reliably measured.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Demographics Characteristics

Table 1: Sample Demographic Characteristics

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
Between 20-30 years	60	40.00%
Between 30-40 years	37	24.70%
More than 40 years	53	35.30%
Total	150	100%
Gender		
Male	75	50.00%
Female	75	50.00%
Total	150	100%
Education		
Doctorate & above	4	2.70%
Post Graduation	94	62.70%
Graduation	52	34.70%
Total	150	100%
Income		
Less than Rs. 1 lakh	8	5.30%
Between Rs. 1-3 lakh	16	10.70%
Between Rs. 3-5 lakh	82	54.70%
More than 5 lakhs	44	29.30%
Total	150	100%

The study's sample consisted of 150 respondents with an equal distribution of males and females (75 each). The age distribution showed that 40.0% of the participants were between 20 and 30 years old, 24.7% were between 30 years and 40 years, and 35.3% were older than 40 years. Regarding educational qualifications, the majority (62.7%) held a postgraduate degree, 34.7% had completed graduation, and 2.7% had attained a doctorate or higher. In terms of income, 5.3% of the respondents earned less than Rs. 1 lakh annually, 10.7% had an income between Rs. 1-3 lakh, 54.7% earned between Rs. 3-5 lakh, and 29.3% had an income exceeding Rs. 5 lakh. This diverse demographic data provides a comprehensive overview of the sample used in the study.

Table 2: Percentage of participants who responded with each score

Item	I	II	III	IV	V	Total
Attitude Towards Organic Food						
A1	3	7.5	37.5	39	13	100
A2	3	14	26	42	15	100
A3	8	17	42	22	11	100
A4	7	15	41	28	9	100
Subjective Norms						
S1	6	17	35	29	13	100
S2	8	11	35	37	9	100
S3	6	18	42	25	9	100

S4	5	15	44	27	9	100
Perceived Behavioural Control						
P1	6	11	42	34	7	100
P2	6	14	41	31	8	100
P3	6	17	37	30	10	100
P4	6	12	39	33	10	100
Customer Purchase Intention						
CP1	5	12	30	36	17	100
CP2	5	10	23	42	20	100
CP3	6	9	22	34	29	100
CP4	6	10	20	27	37	100

The responses across the constructs, given in the table above are summarized as follows:

For **Attitude Towards Organic Food**, the majority of participants showed a neutral stance for items A3 and A4, with 42% and 41% being neutral, respectively. A significant proportion agreed with items A1 and A2, with 39% and 42% agreeing, respectively. Strong agreement was less common but notable for items A1, A2, and A3.

Regarding **Subjective Norms**, most respondents were neutral for items S1, S3, and S4, with 35%, 42%, and 44%, respectively. Agreement was somewhat higher for item S2, with 37% agreeing. Strong agreement was relatively low across all items, ranging from 9% to 13%.

For **Perceived Behavioral Control**, responses were primarily neutral for items P1, P2, and P3, with 42%, 41%, and 37%, respectively. Agreement was notable for all items, with 34% agreeing for P1, 31% for P2, and 30% for P3. Strong agreement was less common but present, ranging from 7% to 10%.

Finally, for **Customer Purchase Intention**, CP1 indicates that 37.2% agree, 31.4% are neutral, and 14.0% strongly agree. For CP2, 41.3% agree, 24.0% are neutral, and 20.7% strongly agree. In CP3, 33.9% agree, 21.5% are neutral, and 30.6% strongly agree. For CP4, 34.7% strongly agree, 28.9% agree, and 19.8% are neutral. These results collectively suggest varied perceptions and intentions towards organic food among the participants.

Scale Reliability

Table 3: Scale Reliability Values

Variables	No. of Items	Cronbach Alpha
Attitude Towards Organic Food	4	.750
Subjective Norms	4	.815
Perceived Behavioral Control	4	.790
Customer Purchase Intention	4	.827

The reliability of the scales used in the study was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha. Each construct was measured using four items. As is given in the table above, the scales for all the constructs are more than the acceptable limit of 0.7.

These reliability coefficients suggest that the scales used to measure the constructs in this study are reliable and consistent.

Moderation Analysis:

Hypothesis (Independent Variable: Attitude Towards Organic Food)

H1: Gender does not moderate the relationship between attitude towards organic food and buying intention.

Table 4: Model Summary:

	R	R ²	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
Model	0.7	0.49	0.29	20.12	5	144	0

The model was statistically significant (F(5, 144)=20.12, p<0, and explained 49% of the variance in customer purchase intention (R²=0.49).

Table 5: Regression Coefficients for Moderated Regression Analysis

	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	2.1	0.58	3.62	0	0.95	3.25
A	0.52	0.16	3.25	0	0.21	0.83
Gender	-0.7	0.3	-2.33	0.02	-1.29	-0.11
Int_1	0.18	0.08	2.25	0.03	0.02	0.34

Table 6: Test(s) of Highest Order Unconditional Interaction(s)

	R ² - chng	F	df1	df2	p
A*Gender	0.02	6.21	1	144	0.02

Table 7: Conditional Impact of Predictors Based on Moderator Levels

Gender	Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
1	0.62	0.07	8.86	0	0.48	0.76
2	0.78	0.08	9.75	0	0.62	0.94

Key Findings:

Regression Coefficients:

- Attitude Towards Organic Food (A)** has a strong positive effect on buying intention, with a coefficient of 0.52 and a significance level of p<0.05. This means that the more positive people feel about organic food, the more likely they are to intend to buy it.
- Gender:** Exhibits a significant negative effect on buying intention (coeff=-0.70, p=0.02). This suggests that gender influences buying intention, with one gender demonstrating lower buying intention compared to the other.
- Interaction Term (A*Gender):** The interaction term is significant (R²-change=0.02, F=6.21, p=0), indicating that gender moderates the relationship between Attitude Towards Organic Food and purchase intention.

Conditional Effects:

- For Male (Gender = 1):** A positive attitude towards organic food significantly increases buying intention, with a strong effect of 0.62. This result is statistically significant, indicating that men who have a positive view of organic food are much more likely to intend to purchase it.
- For Female (Gender = 2):** The effect is 0.78 (SE = 0.08, t = 9.75, p < 0.05). This also shows a significant positive relationship, with a larger effect size compared to Males.

Hypothesis (Independent Variable: Subjective Norms)

H2: Gender does not moderate the relationship between subjective norms and buying intention.

Table 8: Model Summary

	R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
Model	0.55	0.3	0.35	12.43	3	146	0

The overall model was statistically significant ($F(3,146)=12.43, p<0.$) and explained 30% of the variance in customer purchase intention ($R^2=0.30$).

Table 9: Regression Coefficients for Moderated Regression Analysis

	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	2.1	0.6	3.5	0	0.91	3.29
Subjective Norms (N)	0.5	0.12	4.17	0	0.26	0.74
Gender	-0.2	0.15	-1.33	0.18	-0.5	0.1
Int_1 (N*Gender)	0.05	0.08	0.63	0.53	-0.11	0.21

Table 10: Test(s) of Highest Order Unconditional Interaction(s)

	R2-chng	F	df1	df2	p
N*Gender	0.01	0.4	1	146	0.53

Table 11: Conditional Impact of Predictors Based on Moderator Levels

Gender	Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
1 (Male)	0.5	0.12	4.17	0	0.26	0.74
2 (Female)	0.5	0.12	4.17	0	0.26	0.74

Findings

1. Regression Coefficients:

- **Subjective Norms:** A stronger sense of social pressure significantly boosts buying intention, with an effect of 0.50. This means that if people feel more pressure from those around them to buy organic food, they're more likely to intend to make that purchase.
- **Gender:** Gender alone doesn't have a significant impact on buying intention, with a coefficient of -0.20. This indicates that being male or female doesn't greatly influence the intention to buy organic food.
- **Interaction Term (Attitude * Gender):** The interaction between attitude and gender is not significant, suggesting that gender does not change how attitude influences buying intention.

2. Conditional Effects:

- The influence of subjective norms on buying intention is the same for both males and females, with an effect of 0.50. This shows that the impact of social pressure on buying intention is consistent across genders.

4.3.5 Hypotheses (Independent Variable: Perceived Behavioral Control)

H3: Gender does not moderate the relationship between perceived behavioral control and buying intention.

Table 12: Model Summary

	R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
Model	0.54	0.29	0.36	11.23	3	146	0.00

The overall model was statistically significant ($F(3,146)=11.23, p<0.05$) and explained 29% of the variance in customer purchase intention ($R^2=0.29$).

Table 13: Regression Coefficients for Moderated Regression Analysis

	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.95	0.61	3.20	0.00	0.75	3.15
Perceived Behavioural Control (P)	0.47	0.13	3.62	0.00	0.21	0.73
Gender	-0.25	0.16	-1.56	0.12	-0.57	0.07
Int_1 (P*Gender)	0.04	0.09	0.44	0.66	-0.14	0.22

Table 14: Test(s) of Highest Order Unconditional Interaction(s)

	R ² -chng	F	df1	df2	p
P*Gender	0.01	0.20	1	146	0.66

Table 15: Conditional Impact of Predictors Based on Moderator Levels

Gender	Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
1 (Male)	0.47	0.13	3.62	0.00	0.21	0.73
2 (Female)	0.47	0.13	3.62	0.00	0.21	0.73

Key Findings:

Regression Coefficients:

- Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC):** Has a significant positive impact on buying intention (coefficient = 0.47, $p < 0.05$). This means that when people feel they have more control over their behavior, they are more likely to intend to buy organic food.
- Gender:** Does not significantly affect buying intention (coefficient = -0.25, $p = 0.12$). This suggests that gender alone doesn't have a major influence on buying intentions.
- Interaction Term (PBC*Gender):** The interaction term is not significant (R^2 -change = 0.01, $F = 0.20, p = 0.66$). This indicates that gender doesn't change the relationship between perceived behavioral control and buying intention.

Conditional Effects:

The effect of perceived behavioral control on buying intention is 0.47 (SE = 0.13, $t = 3.62, p < 0.05$) for both men and women, meaning there's no significant difference between genders in how perceived control affects buying intentions.

Conclusion

Impact of Gender:

- Attitude Towards Organic Food:** Gender plays a significant role in how attitudes affect buying intentions. Women tend to have stronger positive attitudes toward organic food, which leads to higher buying intentions compared to men.
- Subjective Norms:** Gender does not significantly influence how social norms affect buying intentions. Social influences on purchasing decisions are similar for both men and women.
- Perceived Behavioral Control:** Gender does not significantly affect the relationship between perceived ease of purchasing organic food and buying intentions. Both men and women are equally influenced by how easy or difficult they find buying organic food.

Recommendations

- Targeted Marketing Campaigns:** Given that women have stronger positive attitudes towards organic food, marketers should design campaigns that resonate more with female consumers. Emphasizing health benefits, environmental sustainability, and safety in advertisements can further enhance these attitudes and intentions.
- Educational Initiatives:** Educational programs highlighting the benefits of organic food can be tailored to address both men and women, but with a specific focus on converting the relatively less positive attitudes of men. This can help in broadening the consumer base for organic food products.

3. Leveraging Social Influences:

Since subjective norms play a crucial role in shaping buying intentions regardless of gender, leveraging influencers, community leaders, and social networks to advocate for organic food can enhance its acceptance and consumption.

4. Improving Accessibility and Perceived Control:

To address perceived behavioral control, efforts should be made to improve the availability and affordability of organic food. Policies and initiatives that support local organic farmers, reduce costs, and increase distribution channels can make organic food more accessible to a wider audience.

5. Future Research Directions:

Further research is needed to explore other potential moderating variables such as age, income, and cultural background. Additionally, longitudinal studies can provide insights into how buying intentions and behaviors towards organic food evolve over time.

References

1. Aertsens, J., Mondelaers, K., Verbeke, W., Buysse, J., & Van Huylenbroeck, G. (2009). Personal determinants of organic food consumption: A review. *British Food Journal*, 111(10), 1140-1167.
2. Ahmed, N., Li, C., Khan, A., Qalati, S. A., Naz, S., & Rana, F. (2021). Purchase intention toward organic food among young consumers using the Theory of Planned Behavior: Role of environmental concerns and environmental awareness. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 64(5), 796-822.
3. Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179-211.
4. Armitage, C. J., & Conner, M. (2001). Efficacy of the theory of planned behaviour: A meta-analytic review. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 40(4), 471-499.
5. Aertsens, J., Verbeke, W., Mondelaers, K., & Van Huylenbroeck, G. (2009). Personal determinants of organic food consumption: A review. *British Food Journal*, 111(10), 1140-1167.
6. Arvola, A., Vassallo, M., Dean, M., Lampila, P., Saba, A., Lähteenmäki, L., & Shepherd, R. (2008). Predicting intentions to purchase organic food: The role of affective and moral attitudes in the Theory of Planned Behaviour. *Appetite*, 50(2-3), 443-454.
7. Bravo, C. P., Cordts, A., Schulze, B., & Spiller, A. (2013). Assessing determinants of organic food consumption using data from the German National Nutrition Survey II. *Food Quality and Preference*, 28(1), 60-70.
8. Dean, M., Raats, M. M., & Shepherd, R. (2008). Moral concerns and consumer choice of fresh and processed organic foods. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 38(8), 2088-2107.
9. Gundala, R. R., Nawaz, N., Harindranath, R. M., Boobalan, K., & Gajenderan, V. K. (2022). Does gender moderate the purchase intention of organic foods? Theory of reasoned action. *Heliyon*, 8(9).
10. Hughner, R. S., McDonagh, P., Prothero, A., Shultz, C. J., & Stanton, J. (2007). Who are organic food consumers? A compilation and review of why people purchase organic food. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour: An International Research Review*, 6(2-3), 94-110.
11. Kaur, B., Gangwar, V. P., & Dash, G. (2022). Green marketing strategies, environmental attitude, and green buying intention: A multi-group analysis in an emerging economy context. *Sustainability*, 14(10), 6107.
12. Khare, A. (2015). Antecedents to organic food purchase behavior: Insights from India. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 27(4)
13. Lockie, Stewart & Lyons, Kristen & Lawrence, Geoffrey & Grice, Janet. (2004). Choosing organics: A path analysis of factors underlying the selection of organic food among Australian consumers. *Appetite*. 43. 135-46. 10.1016/j.appet.2004.02.004.
14. Matharu, G. K., von der Heide, T., Sorwar, G., & Sivapalan, A. (2021). What motivates young Indian consumers to buy organic food? *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 34(5), 497-516.
15. Meyers-Levy, J., & Loken, B. (2015). Revisiting gender differences: What we know and what lies ahead. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 25(1), 129-149.
16. Padel, S., & Foster, C. (2005). Exploring the gap between attitudes and behaviour: Understanding why consumers buy or do not buy organic food. *British Food Journal*, 107(8), 606-625.
17. Paul, J., Modi, A., & Patel, J. (2016). Predicting green product consumption using the theory of planned behavior and reasoned action. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 29, 123-134.
18. Sadiq, M. A., Rajeswari, B., Ansari, L., & Kirmani, M. D. (2021). The role of food eating values and exploratory behaviour traits in predicting intention to consume organic foods: An extended planned behaviour approach. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 59, 102352.
19. Singh, A., & Verma, P. (2017). Factors influencing Indian consumers' actual buying behavior towards organic food products. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 167, 473-483.
20. Tarkiainen, A., & Sundqvist, S. (2005). Subjective norms, attitudes and intentions of Finnish consumers in buying organic food. *British Food Journal*, 107(11), 808-822.

21. Vermeir, I., & Verbeke, W. (2008). Sustainable food consumption among young adults in Belgium: Theory of planned behaviour and the role of confidence and values. *Ecological Economics*, 64(3), 542-553.
22. Venkatesh, V., & Morris, M. G. (2000). Why don't men ever stop to ask for directions? Gender, social influence, and their role in technology acceptance and usage behavior. *MIS Quarterly*, 24(1), 115-139.